

INDEX NUMBER.....STUDENT'S SIGNATURE.....

HFNMTC- BEREKUM

END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION

(RGN 23)RGN 124 PERSONAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL HEALTH

TIME ALLOWED 1HR.

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS

- *Answer all questions.*
- *Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.*
- *Each question carries 20 marks.*
- *Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers.*
- *Note that any number of points provide beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.*

QUESTION ONE

- a. State **THREE (3)** factors and explain briefly how bowel elimination of an individual can be affected. - **3MARKS**
- b. Mention **FOUR (4)** complications of poor mouth care. - **2MARKS**
- c. State and explain the **FOUR (4)** concepts of health. - **6MARKS**
- d. As a nurse you have been invited by the chief of Dombra for a health talk on safe drinking water. The people after the education decided to construct a well, how would you educate them on **FIVE (5)** safety precautions in construction of a well. - **5MARKS**
- e. Mention **EIGHT (8)** methods of waste disposal - **4MARKS**

QUESTION TWO

- a. State and explain the **FOUR (4)** ethical principles of environmental health. - **4MARKS**
- b. Mention **SEVEN (7)** factors affecting health. - **7MARKS**
- c. In what **SEVEN (7)** ways would you educate a group of in a church you were invited to, as a on selection of site for healthful housing - **7MARKS.**
- d. State **two (2)** ways of waste minimization in health care. - **2MARKS.**

RESPECT YOU LEARN TO CARE
YOU MUST CARE TO LEARN.

MS. ANTOINETTE EFUM

INDEX NUMBER-----STUDENT'S SIGNATURE-----

HFNMTC - BEREKUM

END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – 23RD SEPTEMBER 2021
(RM 18) RMD 123: PERSONAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL HEALTH

TIME ALLOWED: 1 HOUR

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers.
- Note that any number of points provide beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

QUESTION ONE

Madam Akuba, a 67 year old woman has been admitted to the hospital with diagnosis of hemiplegia. The medical officer has ordered her to undergo exercise at the physiotherapy department. At the physiotherapy department, the physiotherapist inform her that she will be taken through passive exercise

- a. Explain to madam Akuba and relatives what passive exercise is. - 2MARKS
- b. Identify any **THREE (3)** factors that can influence exercise - 3MARKS
- c. Explain to her **EIGHT (8)** benefits of exercise - 8MARKS

Madam Akuba informed you that she has difficulty in sleeping and need sleep pills. However you decided to teach her good sleeping habits instead of the sleep pills

- d. State any **SIX (6)** sleep disorders - 3MARKS
- e. What pre-sleeping habits will you teach her and her relatives? - 4MARKS

QUESTION TWO

During a community outreach programme, you observed that Nyanyano community practice crude dumping. As a result you consulted the assembly member and the Odikro for a health talk at a durbar.

- a. Briefly explain crude dumping - 2MARKS
- b. Apart from crude dumping state **FOUR (4)** other methods of refuse disposal? - 2MARKS
- c. Describe **EIGHT (8)** health hazards of crude dumping - 8MARKS

During the observation of the refuse, you realized that some of them are hazardous waste.

- d. What **FOUR (4)** characteristics must a waste possess to be classified as a hazardous waste? - 4 MARKS
- e. In recommending dustbin for the community, what **FOUR (4)** characteristics will you encourage them to look out for before buying the dustbin? - 4MARKS

MR. JOSEPH APPIAH

GRAND TOTAL

50

NAME OF EXAMINER:

INDEX NUMBER:

SIGNATURE OF EXAMINER:

HFNMTC – BEREKUM/ ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO

END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION, MAY 2018

RGN 20 AND RM 15 PERSONAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL HEALTH

TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HRS

ESSAY

Instructions

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

QUESTION ONE

- a. Identify five ways of caring for the hair - 5marks
- b. State four (4) reasons for combing the hair - 4marks
- c. Mention five (5) problems associated with the hair - 5marks
- d. State the three types of pediculosis and the area of the body they infect. - 6marks

QUESTION TWO

- a. Identify three (3) methods by which solid refuse can be managed - 3marks
- b. State any four (4) characteristics a good refuse bin (dust bin) should have - 4marks.
- c. Describe eight (8) effects of improper refuse disposal - 8marks
- d. Outline five (5) examples of water borne diseases - 5marks

QUESTION THREE

- a. State any eight feature of a good housing - 8marks
- b. Mention any three (3) statutory bodies in the housing industry. - 3marks
- c. What are some of the challenges facing the housing industry in Ghana? - 5marks
- d. Describe any four (4) effects of overcrowding - 4marks

NMTC- BEREKUM/ST MARYS COMPUS DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – MAY 2016
D 18 & RM 13 PERSONAL AND ENVIROMENTAL HEALTH
TIME ALLOWED: 2 HRS

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks

Question one

- a. State four (4) factors that influence personal hygiene - 4marks
- b. Poor personal hygiene has many effects on the health an individual. List seven (7) effects of poor personal hygiene - 7marks
- c. Enumerate any five (5) guidelines for good posture - 5marks
- d. Mention four (4) effects of neglected mouth - 4marks

Question two

- a. Identify any five ways of caring for the hair - 5marks
- b. State the three (3) types of pediculosis and the area of the body they infect - 6marks
- c. State five (5) measures to promote good sleep - 5marks
- d. State the four (4) functions of sleep - 4marks

Question three

- a. Enumerate four (4).effects of overcrowding. - 4marks
- b. State any six (6) determinants of a good housing. - 6marks
- c. State any two (2) qualities of a good latrine. - 2marks
- d. State any four (4) regulatory bodies managing food safety in Ghana. - 2marks
- e. How can water be contaminated at the source? - 6marks

Question Four

Air is a mixture of gases that envelope the earth

- a. State the composition of air. - 4marks.
- b. How can household pests be controlled - 5marks
- c. Mention the three forms of artificial ventilation. - 3marks
- d. Solid waste (refuse) can be disposed off in many ways. List any five (5) ways of solid waste disposal - 5marks
- e. State three (3) effects of improper waste disposal. - 3marks

NMTC – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – MAY 2012
DIPLOMA 15, HRGN 026/HMDW024 PERSONAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL HEALTH
TIME ALLOWED: 2 Hrs.
ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

- a. i. What is a house? - 2 marks
- ii. Describe the three (3) types of house you know - 9 marks
- Mention two (2) types each of natural and artificial ventilation - 4 marks
- i. State three (3) factors that govern the amount of natural lighting in a room - 3 marks
- ii. Gives two (2) examples of artificial lighting - 2 marks

Question Two

- a. i. What are the two (2) main types or stages sleep - 2 marks
- ii. Explain any four (4) measures that can be done to promote good sleep - 8 marks
- b. Mention two (2) ways by which contamination of water can be prevented - 2 marks
- c. List four (4) ways of maintaining clothing - 2 marks
- d. Mention four (4) effects of poor personal hygiene on health - 2 marks
- e. State four (4) benefits of exercise - 4 marks

Question Three

- a. Explain permanent hard water - 2 marks
- b. Mention and describe the first three (3) methods of large scale purification of water - 6 marks
- c. i. List four (4) diseases that can be spread by housefly - 2 marks
- ii. Mention four (4) diseases that can be caused by mosquitoes - 2 marks
- d. State eight (8) ways by which houseflies can be prevented - 8 marks

Question Four

- a. i. What is food? - 1 mark
- ii. Mention eight (8) food related diseases you know - 4 marks
- b. Mention eight (8) precautions to be taken in preparation of food - 8 marks
- c. i. State five (5) importance of food - 2 ½ marks
- ii. Mention three (3) disadvantages of storages and preservation of food - 1 ½ mark
- d. i. List three (3) factors to consider in food production - 1 ½ mark
- ii. State three (3) processes to consider before transporting food - 1 ½ mar

NMTC- BEREKUM/ST MARYS COMPUS DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – MAY 2016
D 18 & RM 13 PERSONAL AND ENVIROMENTAL HEALTH
TIME ALLOWED: 2 HRS
ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks

Question one

- a. State four (4) factors that influence personal hygiene - 4marks
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- c. Enumerate any five (5) guidelines for good posture - 5marks
- Mention four (4) effects of neglected mouth - 4marks

Question two

- a. Identify any five ways of caring for the hair - 5marks
- b. State the three (3) types of pediculosis and the area of the body they infect - 6marks
- c. State five (5) measures to promote good sleep - 5marks
- d. State the four (4) functions of sleep - 4marks

Question three

- a. Enumerate four (4) effects of overcrowding. - 4marks
- b. State any six (6) determinants of a good housing. - 6marks
- c. State any two (2) qualities of a good latrine. - 2marks
- d. State any four (4) regulatory bodies managing food safety in Ghana. - 2marks
- e. How can water be contaminated at the source? - 6marks

Question Four

Air is a mixture of gases that envelope the earth

- a. State the composition of air. - 4marks.
- b. How can household pests be controlled - 5marks
- c. Mention the three forms of artificial ventilation. - 3marks
- d. Solid waste (refuse) can be disposed off in many ways. List any five (5) ways of solid waste disposal - 5marks
- e. State three (3) effects of improper waste disposal. - 3marks

AMTC - BERENJEM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION - APRIL 2013
DIPLOMA IN HRGN 026/HMDW024 PERSONAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL HEALTH
TIME ALLOWED: 2 Hrs.
ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

- | | | | | |
|----|-----|--|---|---------|
| a. | i. | What is a house? | - | 2 marks |
| | ii. | Describe the three (3) types of house you know | - | 9 marks |
| b. | | Mention two (2) types each of natural and artificial ventilation | - | 4 marks |
| | i. | State three (3) factors that govern the amount of natural lighting in a room | - | 3 marks |
| | ii. | Gives two (2) examples of artificial lighting | - | 2 marks |

Question Two

- | | | | | |
|----|-----|---|---|---------|
| a. | i. | What are the two (2) main types or stages sleep | - | 2 marks |
| | ii. | Explain any four (4) measures that can be done to promote good sleep | - | 8 marks |
| b. | | Mention two (2) ways by which contamination of water can be prevented | - | 2 marks |
| c. | | List four (4) ways of maintaining clothing | - | 2 marks |
| d. | | Mention four (4) effects of poor personal hygiene on health | - | 2 marks |
| e. | | State four (4) benefits of exercise | - | 4 marks |

Question Three

- | | | | | |
|----|-----|---|---|---------|
| a. | | Explain permanent hard water | - | 2 marks |
| b. | | Mention and describe the first three (3) methods of large scale purification of water | - | 6 marks |
| | i. | List four (4) diseases that can be spread by housefly | - | 2 marks |
| | ii. | Mention four (4) diseases that can be caused by mosquitoes | - | 2 marks |
| | | State eight (8) ways by which houseflies can be prevented | - | 8 marks |

Question Four

- | | | | | |
|----|-----|--|---|-----------|
| a. | i. | What is food? | - | 1 mark |
| | ii. | Mention eight (8) food related diseases you know | - | 4 marks |
| b. | | Mention eight (8) precautions to be taken in preparation of food | - | 8 marks |
| c. | i. | State five (5) importance of food | - | 2 ½ marks |
| | ii. | Mention three (3) disadvantages of storages and preservation of food | - | 1 ½ mark |
| d. | i. | List three (3) factors to consider in food production | - | 1 ½ mark |
| | ii. | State three (3) processes to consider before transporting food | - | 1 ½ mark |

HF NMTC- BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – OCTOBER, 2020
RGN 22/ RMI7 (RGN 123) HEALTH PROMOTION
TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HR

INSTRUCTIONS

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provide beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will attract any mark

Question One

The process of community diagnosis involves four stages

- | | |
|--|----------|
| a. State the <i>four (4)</i> stages of community diagnosis | - 4marks |
| b. Explain the <i>four(4)</i> stages stated above | - |
| 8marks | |
| c. Define community diagnosis | - 2marks |
| d. State and explain <i>three (3)</i> types of needs | - 6marks |

Question Two

Stigmatization has been identified as one of the social factors affecting health care delivery in the country which needs to be addressed if the goal of achieving health for all is to be realized.

- | | | |
|------|--|-----------|
| a. | | |
| i. | What is stigmatization | - 2 marks |
| ii. | State <i>five (5)</i> factors that lead to fear and stigma | - 5 marks |
| iii. | State <i>five(5)</i> effects of stigmatization on individual | - 5 marks |
| b. | | |
| i. | What is gender mainstreaming | 2 marks |
| ii. | Explain <i>SIX (6)</i> roles of the nurse in gender issues | 6marks |

Question Three

Miss Cinderella, a 26-year-old lady is engaged to Mr. Diego and later planned to get married after five years of dating. Two weeks to the wedding, Mr. Diego broke up with Miss Cinderella and this made her unable to cope with events of life leading to the feeling of guilt, anxiety, depression and self-destruction. She was therefore taken to a psychiatry hospital where she was referred to see a counselor for crisis counseling.

- | | | |
|----|---|------------|
| a. | What is counseling | - 2 mark |
| b. | State <i>three (3)</i> characteristics of an ideal counseling environment | - 3 marks |
| c. | Explain the REDI approach to counseling | - 12 marks |
| e. | State <i>three(3)</i> factors affecting interpersonal communication | - 3 marks |

